

Scientific use cases for cross-domain sensitive data research in the UK

May 2024

The PSC

Acknowledgements

The PSC (Public Service Consultants) were commissioned by DARE UK (Data and Analytics and Research Environments UK) from November 2023 – March 2024 to surface use cases for sensitive data connectivity in the UK. The authors would like to thank all participants for giving their time and sharing their ideas during the workshop.

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The PSC exists to make public services brilliant for organisations, society and individuals. The PSC works with clients using data science and user centred-design to co-create new digital services, ensuring they deliver strong financial results, are in harmony with teams and working practices, and include everyone. The PSC's expertise has been recognised by the Financial Times, The Economist, The Guardian, and the Health Service Journal.

The PSC

Foreword

The grand challenges facing society today are ever more complex and interconnected. Beginning to understand these challenges requires intersectional research that combines different kinds of data about people. DARE UK's vision is for research and innovation to benefit from seamless, secure use of diverse sensitive data, at a pace, efficiency and scale approaching that of the open data ecosystem, in ways that revolutionise research productivity and accelerate research to deliver public good.

The energy and enthusiasm during this workshop from both researchers and members of the public clearly evidenced the demand for linking different types of data together to tackle truly intersectional societal problems that simply cannot be understood by studying factors in isolation from one another. To achieve our vision, it is essential that we keep the priorities of both the data users and the beneficiaries of such research and innovation at the heart of what we do.

As we look towards the next phase of DARE UK we will continue to work with researchers, the public and the wider data research ecosystem to deliver impactful science. We hope that these use cases illustrate the compelling societal benefits that could be unlocked if we bring together different types of sensitive data at scale. I would like to extend my heartfelt thanks to the researchers and public representatives for the time they have given in supporting us in this work.

May 2024

Emily Jefferson
Interim Director, DARE UK

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1 / About this work

On 8 February 2024 DARE UK, supported by The PSC brought together 48 UK-based researchers and seven public participants to surface use cases for linking sensitive data. Across a full-day workshop, we examined how linked sensitive data in the UK could be brought together to enable research that benefits the public.

Executive summary

Workshop participants met to work through a series of interactive discussions and activities to explore the possibilities created by linking different types of sensitive data together at scale. Although the focus of the workshop was on sensitive data linkages, participants were also invited to think about different types of non-sensitive data that could supplement sensitive data linkages for further insights. The outputs have been synthesised, analysed, and quantified to provide a detailed breakdown of the high priority research opportunities to inform the next phase of the DARE UK programme.

The use cases surfaced highlight the breadth of the opportunity that a connected sensitive data infrastructure could deliver for research for public benefit in the UK.

We learned about the practical applications of cross-domain research to help understand and solve some of the UK's most pressing societal challenges, demonstrating the potential for bringing together interdisciplinary expertise with cross-cutting data to make a real difference.

This short exercise has served as an exciting proof of concept for the sorts of real-world use cases that bringing together different types of data can enable, and will inform and help define the specifications future funding opportunities in the next phase of the DARE UK programme.

Summary of key findings

Participants surfaced a total of 52 different use cases that, as a collection, were notable across three overarching themes: their diversity, their potential impact, and their innovative approaches to solving some of the most pressing societal challenges facing the UK today.

The first theme was around the **diversity of different data types** that the use cases represented. The 52 use cases brought together a total of 80 different kinds of data that could be grouped into 10 different higher-level data domains.

Use cases were cross-cutting, with 69% of use cases bringing together three or more different domains of data to answer their research question. Health data was used in 85% of use cases, but in broad ways and with improved health outcomes often as a secondary motivation: typically use cases focused on improving public health, wellbeing and productivity and only one use case targeted a specific clinical intervention.

The second notable theme that emerged was that use cases looked to understand some of the **most pressing societal**

challenges facing the UK. The use cases gravitated towards tackling many of the UK's most persistent challenges, with over half of the use cases addressing long-standing challenges facing UK society dating back from the 1970s and '80s.

These included use cases looking at understanding:

- **Rising social inequality, 27% of use cases**
- **The flat-lining of UK productivity since the financial crash of 2008 known as the 'Productivity Paradox', 23% of use cases**
- **Systemic challenges such as Climate change, 15% of use cases**

Other use cases focused on new opportunities for understanding modern challenges that are evolving in nature, including the infiltration of digital technologies such as social media into all aspects of modern life and its impact on the wellbeing of children and young people in particular.

Finally, use cases were innovative in their approaches for linking data. For example, 38% of use cases looked to combine data at the level of the family or household to enable analysis of the impact of our social (and not just physical) environments on our health, future life outcomes and opportunities.

The 10 higher-level data domains

ECONOMIC

HEALTH

SOCIAL

COMMERCIAL

CONSUMER

CLIMATE AND ENVIRONMENT

LIFESTYLE

CARE AND SOCIAL SYSTEM

GEOGRAPHIC

JUSTICE

Deeper dives into use cases revealed tremendous societal and economic benefit opportunities.

10 use cases voted most critical by participants were taken forward for more detailed exploration, listed below:

Use case	Title	
1	Transforming the food economy	→
2	Addressing domestic abuse	→
3	Reducing NHS bottlenecks	→
4	Addressing children's mental health	→
5	Understanding long-term unemployment	→
6	Family interventions to tackle childhood obesity	→
7	Addressing unmet need and improving access to primary care	→
8	Balancing healthy diets with sustainable production	→
9	Improving vaccine uptake	→
10	Understanding and enhancing low emission zones	→

In addition to the societal benefits that could be realised through improved understanding of the challenges presented by these use cases, the potential economic benefits of addressing the challenges identified in these prioritised use cases was estimated at £319.11bn (+/-£79.14bn) to 2050.

Clearly, much additional work will need to be done to convert any research findings from these use cases into policies and actions that could bring about these real-world benefits, but this economic modelling illustrates how research to support addressing even a small subsection of the use cases surfaced during this workshop could bring tremendous public benefit.

As the DARE UK programme moves into the next phase, it is critical, as evidenced by this work, that the programme supports the delivery of real-world interdisciplinary data research studies that span traditional research boundaries and positively impact our collective understanding of intersectional societal challenges. This work will be used to inform and define the specifications of future funding opportunities for research teams whose ambitions are to begin tackling the sorts of use cases identified in this report.

About DARE UK

DARE UK has been initiated by UKRI to design and deliver a national data research infrastructure that is joined-up, demonstrates trustworthiness and supports research at scale for the public good. The programme's scope includes all research conducted by UKRI that uses, or anticipates the use of, sensitive data from different research disciplines and sectors. DARE UK is being designed in an open and inclusive manner, with involvement from researchers, technologists and the public embedded throughout.

The DARE UK vision is for all research and innovation to benefit from seamless, secure use of diverse sensitive data, at a pace, efficiency and scale approaching that of the open data ecosystem, and in ways that revolutionise research productivity and accelerate research to deliver public good.

Critical to achieving this vision is the identification of key research priorities and use cases that demonstrate the tremendous scientific potential that a more connected sensitive data research infrastructure can enable. This will ensure that the infrastructure capabilities that DARE UK supports help researchers to tackle the societal challenges that are most important to the public.

This piece of work, bringing together researchers and members of the public, formulates potential scientific use cases that could address key societal challenges by bringing together cross-domain sensitive data. These use cases will serve to shape the activities of the next phase of the DARE UK programme, specifically informing the structure of funding calls for cross-domain research exemplars that will work together with infrastructure development teams and Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to address major societal challenges.

Definitions

Benefits modelling:

The exercise of defining the potential benefits of an intervention (e.g. reduced waste, extended healthy life span) and using evidence to quantify the impact that the benefits could have. Typically, multiple sources are used and include uncertainty ranges, calculated in a 'model'.

Data linkage and analysis:

Researchers link records from the same individuals across different datasets (for example, their education records and subsequent employment records) to better understand how different factors in people's lives affect one another. Connecting information from different places and sectors like this can reveal meaningful insights about populations without disclosing identifiable information about individuals. By analysing sensitive data across domains, researchers can better understand how society works, with the findings allowing us to develop better policies and services that benefit the public.

Sensitive data:

Data which contains personally identifiable information such as names, addresses and identifying numbers, or commercially sensitive information such as retail information

and confidential product details. Even data which has been 'de-identified' (e.g. has had names and addresses removed) can still be sensitive as there is potential for re-identification, especially when linked with other data.

Trusted Research Environments (TREs):

TREs are safe, secure computing environments. They typically hold de-identified sensitive data, from a range of sources, for research and innovation purposes. TREs are the 'safe settings' where researchers access sensitive data for research, via a rigorous approval process. Data is accessed by approved researchers, and only for approved projects in the public interest. The data stays in the TRE and is not downloaded to the researcher's own system, and outputs leaving the TRE are rigorously checked to make sure that they do not contain any potentially identifiable data.

Use cases:

A simple way to describe how linking sensitive (and non-sensitive) data at scale can achieve specific outcomes and benefits.

2 / Our approach

On 8 February 2024 we hosted a Use Case Identification Workshop, bringing together interdisciplinary researchers and a public panel to collaboratively define the future research potential and societal grand challenges that could be addressed through the DARE UK vision of a national, joined-up sensitive data research infrastructure.

The workshop aimed to answer the question:

“If all sensitive data in the UK could be linked, and accessible at scale, how could we use it to benefit the public?”

The workshop centred around a series of four interactive activities and discussions to surface high-priority use cases for linking sensitive data.

1 Identifying sensitive data

Identifying different types of sensitive data. Although the focus of the workshop was on sensitive data linkages, participants were also invited to think about different types of non-sensitive data that could supplement sensitive data linkages for further insights

2 Challenge landscapes

Recognising some of the most pressing challenges and unanswered questions affecting UK society

3 Surfacing use cases

Bringing together outputs from activities (1) and (2) to generate use cases addressing specific societal challenges through linking sensitive data

4 “Dragons’ Den” prioritisation

Developing priority use cases and pitching those that participants believed offered greatest public benefit

Each workshop activity was designed to ensure individuals could participate regardless of their background and experience - no prior knowledge was assumed.

Discussion was focussed on uncovering what could be possible if all sensitive data was linked at scale, rather than how (technically or in terms of governance) this data would be linked. All activities were therefore approached with the following assumptions in mind:

Assumption 1: All data (sensitive and non-sensitive) that is currently collected is accessible for research.

Assumption 2: All sensitive data is held securely within TREs.

Assumption 3: All data (both sensitive and non-sensitive) can be safely and securely linked together, at scale.

Each activity began with a short presentation introducing the exercise, before participants divided into groups of 5-8 individuals, supported by a facilitator from either the DARE UK delivery team or The PSC. Where possible, members of the public were distributed across the groups to ensure the public perspective was considered by all. Participants were encouraged to change groups between the first three exercises, to maximise cross-disciplinary discussion and encourage participants to think and connect with others beyond their areas of expertise.

To ensure the discussion topics were captured, participants were given templates to fill out as part of each activity, with

facilitators supporting groups to write down any additional insights as required.

Use case prioritisation

Participants first generated a broad range of use cases (Activity 3), identifying the types of sensitive data involved and the outcomes and benefits that could be achieved as a result. For all the use cases that their group identified, participants within each group were given three votes to assign to those use cases they felt offered the greatest public benefit. This gave an early indication of the different use cases each group felt offered the greatest potential for impact. In the dragon’s den exercise (Activity 4), we asked groups to agree one use case that they would present to the group, using the earlier voting to aid their selection.

The use cases highlighted in this report demonstrate the breadth of use cases selected. We filtered use cases by those including at least three different domain linkages, and then selected those prioritized by participants (from both the dragon’s den exercise and earlier voting) to demonstrate the breadth and depth of potential outcomes, whilst avoiding duplicates. This meant one use case from the dragon’s den exercise was excluded, as it considered sensitive data from only one domain, whilst two additional use cases not showcased during the dragon’s den were included. The two additional use cases were selected on the basis of both their votes, but also for including sufficient detail for benefits modelling.

Desk research

All insights from the workshop were categorised in a use case database which recorded the data types linked, the intended interventions, desired outcomes, and potential benefits to the public. This database served as the foundation for all analysis.

We supplemented the insights captured on the day with desk research and benefits modelling to understand the potential impact that these use cases could realise in greater detail.

Deploying an outcome-based approach we sought to quantify the direct economic and wider social benefits of use cases. At a high level, this process involved:

1. Identifying the primary challenges addressed by each use case and obtaining the latest estimates for the financial impacts of these challenges, both in direct economic and wider social terms, via a mini literature review.
2. Breaking down the primary challenges into distinct 'outcome areas', based upon the intended interventions and outcomes provided by participants. For example, tackling childhood obesity (Use Case 6) was disaggregated into lifetime healthcare, productivity, and quality of life costs, in addition to spillover effects on other household members.
3. Estimating the potential percentage impact that each intervention would have on its specified 'outcome area'. Where possible, these estimates were informed by case studies of comparable interventions both within the UK and internationally (references in Appendix 4). In cases where such studies were unavailable, conservative estimates were developed by two analysts independently to establish upper and lower bounds for the estimated impact, indicating the range of potential uncertainty.

4. Multiplying the percentage impact by the estimated size of the 'outcome area' to determine the potential benefit of each intervention. We then aggregated these estimates to provide the final assessment of total economic benefit (see left).

Together, these activities highlighted both the breadth and depth of different use cases that could be realised through DARE UK's work.

Senior Leaders Roundtable

The preliminary findings from the workshop were shared with a group of senior leaders from interested organisations and Research Councils involved in supporting research using sensitive data. This further stimulated conversation about the benefits of cross-domain collaboration and merits of a 'use case-focused' approach to surmount siloes and barriers.

Plenary session

Workshop attendees were invited back for a 1-hour plenary session on 11 March 2024. This played back the key findings and use-cases to participants, and allowed for further feedback to be incorporated into the work. The invite was open to all attendees and 20 participants joined the session.

“It’s been an eye-opener for me because often we tend to work in our own little silos and we don’t really connect with people outside, and sometimes we don’t realise that actually the problems that we’re facing or the opportunities that we are thinking about are also shared among people and not just in our own discipline but in other sectors as well.”

Workshop participant

Rationale for our approach

The approach outlined above was designed to breakdown existing siloes within participants’ thinking and to encourage researchers to conceptualise sensitive data connectivity beyond their areas of expertise. When implemented with our three opportunity-focused assumptions, this enabled us to capture both the breadth and diversity of the opportunities for linking sensitive data. Through further economic benefit analysis, we can demonstrate the huge potential of an enhanced sensitive data infrastructure, not only in terms of possible use cases but also their potential impact on society.

Recruitment

Participants for the Use Case Identification Workshop were recruited by invitation as well as through an open call for expressions of interest, shared via DARE UK’s social media channels. Participants included PhD students, post-docs, professors and government policy professionals, plus public representatives. Participants self-identified as working across a total of seven different Research Councils (see figure 1a for full breakdown), illustrating the diversity of research subject expertise in the room. In addition, over half of the researchers identified as working across two or more different research councils (figure 1b), indicating that the majority of researcher participants were themselves working at the boundaries of multiple research domains.

Public participation

If the true value of data for public benefit is to be realised, the public must be taken along the journey and invited to contribute in a meaningful way. Public participants contributed to activities throughout the workshop, in addition to contributing to the planning of the workshop session itself.

“I enjoyed the opportunity to meet with other, varied stakeholders (including Patient and Public representatives) with an interest in this space.”
 Workshop participant

Figure 1a:
 Number of participants self-identifying with each research council

Figure 1b:
 Number of participants self-identifying with each research council

Strengths and limitations of the approach

Workshop activities were carefully designed to assume no prior knowledge of sensitive data research, aiming to equip researchers and public contributors with the information needed to develop a range of use cases that highlight the opportunities linking sensitive data could bring. The breadth of use cases surfaced allow DARE UK to better understand the benefit to the public of linking such data, and the types of data that need to be linked to achieve this.

Whilst participant recruitment achieved a broad spread of representation across research councils, a sample of 48 researchers is unlikely to be truly representative of the breadth of research activity interested in the use of sensitive data within the UK. Similarly, a sample of seven public contributors will not truly reflect the diversity of public opinion around the most pressing research priorities for the use of sensitive data. Finally, the workshop was focussed on hearing the perspectives of academics, government policy researchers and the public; it did not include representatives from industry (other than participants with industry affiliations through Innovate UK). Further work would be required to understand industry perspectives on the range of public benefit that could be achieved through linking sensitive data.

Workshop participants identified a range of use cases that linked different data sources for public benefit. The granularity of detail on the data to be linked varied, potentially due to

researchers' own familiarity with the datasets in question, and the challenge to highlight the breadth as well of depth of opportunity within the time available. Workshop participants voted for use cases they felt offered the greatest potential for public impact, working these examples up in greater detail – some of which are included in the use case deep dives of this report.

This prioritisation process was however subjective and may have been influenced by the behaviour of other participants. These use cases should therefore be interpreted as a broad illustration of the types of benefits that DARE UK could realise through linking sensitive data, rather than those which offer the greatest quantifiable benefit in total.

“I really wanted to engage with people from multiple disciplines, from various walks of life, who are interested in not just education but in health, in criminal justice in social care, and I think that’s exactly what the event has given me - the platform to interact with people.”

Workshop participant

3 / Findings

DARE UK is uniquely placed to support research for the public good through use cases that are diverse, impactful, and innovative.

Through the workshop activities, participants surfaced 52 different use cases which were notable for:

1/ Their diversity

Use cases were cross-disciplinary, linking data from a diverse range of domains to address their research questions.

2/ Their impact

Use cases targeted high impact areas, focussing on addressing many of the most pressing challenges facing the UK population.

3/ Their innovative approaches to solving these problems

Use cases leveraged sensitive data to offer new ideas for tackling problems in order to reveal novel insights.

Theme 1:

Use cases brought together a **diverse** range of data sources

Participants identified a range of data across different domains

Participants identified a range of both sensitive and non-sensitive data, which could be grouped under 10 broad categories:

Participants generated 52 use cases for connecting data across domains

Participants linked **80** distinct data types to develop **52** different use cases, and **69%** of use cases linked data across **three+ domains**.

The graphic right illustrates the strength of these linkages, with the size of the domain name reflecting the number of times the domain was used, and the thickness of each line the number of connections between each domain. For example, **Health** and **Social** are the most strongly linked domains, being linked together in 26 of the 52 use cases. Meanwhile **Health** and **Commercial** data were linked just once.

“Interestingly, an awful lot of people talked about health benefits, but the health benefits that could be achieved by linking different types of data. So everything from transport to environment to education, employment, wealth etc. ”

Participant feedback

This helps us understand which linkages might be the most 'in demand' and find untapped opportunities

Health and **Economic** data were drawn upon most often, and were linked to every other domain at least once. They were most strongly linked to social data and each other.

Health data was used in **85%** of use cases, but in broad ways and with improved health outcomes often as a secondary effect: typically use cases focused on improving public health, wellbeing and productivity and only one targeted a specific clinical condition.

Commercial data was linked to **six** of the nine domains, but the relationships were relatively weak. **Commercial** data was linked just once to **Health, Economic, Consumer, Lifestyle,** and **Geographical** data; although it was linked to **Climate** data in three use cases.

Justice and **Social Care** data were linked to other domains less frequently, but were well integrated with **Social, Health,** and **Economic** domains.

Within each domain, a diverse range of data was identified

The infographic right is a snapshot of the data mentioned within each domain. These data descriptions were taken from the written outputs that participants created, representing ‘verbatim’ terms. Some data types could fall into a couple of different domains, and so we have categorised them based on the context of the use case in question.

This deeper look at in-demand data illustrates just how diverse our data-sources could be: government departments, local authorities, health records, the census, individuals’ devices, or supermarket loyalty cards to name a few.

The chosen research methodology captured the insights of participants verbatim. To ensure an accurate representation

of participants’ thoughts, we have chosen to record insights exactly as they were recorded, without adjusting for differences in inferred meaning. Consequently, we did not conduct further quantitative analysis of data types at this level of granularity, although this may be an interesting area to explore in the future to help understand which datasets and dataset-level linkages are in greatest demand.

“What I really liked about what we did was we were not just looking at the most obvious data sources. We were thinking outside the box, and that was a theme that came across the entire day today.”

Workshop participant

Theme 2:

Use cases targeted **high-impact** areas, addressing major UK challenges

The use cases gravitated towards tackling many of the UK's most persistent challenges

Over half of the use cases focussed on addressing persistent challenges facing UK society from the 1980s, if not before. As shown below, they included health challenges such as obesity, economic challenges such as the UK productivity crisis, the systemic challenge of inequality and the global issue of climate change. These challenges are interconnected – for example climate change has unequal effects, exacerbating inequalities.

Inequality 27%

UK income inequality is up slightly in the 2019/20 financial year
Gini coefficient for disposable income

Source: ONS © FT

In the UK, inequality persists across education, employment, healthcare access, and opportunity. With some of the highest levels of income inequality in Europe, this disparity undermines social cohesion and economic prosperity, hindering the overall well-being and potential of individuals and communities.^{1,2}

Climate change 15%

Temperatures in 2020 close to highest ever
Mean temperature in the UK 1884-2020 (°C)

Source: Met Office

Climate has wide-ranging impacts on health, the economy, and ecosystems. With climate change damages estimated to cost 3% of GDP annually by 2050, rising temperatures, extreme weather, and increased disruptions threaten the way of life across our society.^{3,4}

Productivity 23%

UK productivity growth has been dire since the financial crisis
Index, 2019=100

Sources: ONS, FT calculations © FT

Since the 2008 financial crisis, the UK has grappled with a sustained productivity crisis, marked by sluggish growth rates and a persistent gap compared to other leading economies.^{5,6} Overcoming this challenge is crucial for fostering social mobility, improving well-being, and creating opportunities for future generations.

Obesity 13%

Share of adults that are obese, 1975 to 2016

Source: Met Office

Addressing obesity has long been a significant challenge for policymakers. With more than a quarter of UK adults classified as obese, it poses a major public health concern, leading to various chronic diseases, straining healthcare resources, and diminishing overall quality of life.^{7,8}

They also offered new opportunities for understanding modern challenges that are evolving in nature...

Over the past decade, UK society has undergone a profound transformation, rendering many of the traditional approaches to understanding and addressing challenges increasingly unsuitable. We are now more cognisant than ever of the interconnected nature of societal challenges, and therefore the need for interdisciplinary solutions to effectively tackle them. Moreover, in an increasingly data-driven era, there is a growing recognition of the huge potential to leverage data at scale to provide a deeper understanding and develop robust predictions.

Participants highlighted several pivotal shifts, and their causes, that have transformed our society over the past decade. Two of the most prominent being:

The COVID-19 pandemic:

The disruption of the COVID-19 pandemic and its long-term effects redefined how we work, socialise, and approach everyday life, almost overnight. This transformation strained already limited resources, with disruptions and heightened demand amplifying pressure on essential services.

Technology and social media:

The explosion of social media and the proliferation of digital technologies into all aspects of modern life, has precipitated a rapid reimagining of how we learn, communicate, and build relationships. With a disproportionate impact upon the youngest members of society.

...and addressing the impact of these

Unhealthy modern lifestyles

31%

Exploring improved approaches for individuals and communities to thrive in their natural, built, and social surroundings, making decisions that enhance health, well-being, productivity, and longevity. For example: Transforming how we produce, consume, and interact with our food economy ([Use case 1](#)).

Mental health

27%

Understanding the root causes of mental health challenges to develop holistic, lifelong, and preventative approaches that maximise individuals' capacity to lead happy, healthy, and fulfilling lives. For example: Addressing children's mental health early to minimise long term consequences ([Use case 4](#)).

Educational outcomes

19%

Ensuring equitable access to educational opportunities and outcomes, creating a system capable of meeting the diverse needs of the population and providing every individual with an equal start in life. For example: Understanding how educational access and attainment can impact long term unemployment and developing mitigating strategies ([Use case 5](#)).

Theme 3:

Use cases were **innovative** in their approach, considering new ways of understanding old problems

Participants identified key benefits of looking beyond the individual to link sensitive data across family units and households

Workshop participants frequently underlined the importance of connecting sensitive data across families and households, whether they are related socially or biologically. Many emphasised that the entire life journey, from childhood to old age, is profoundly influenced by the environments we inhabit and the individuals we share these with. To best understand the root causes and critical interactions that shape experiences and outcomes across society it is therefore vital to effectively measure and evaluate these factors at a collective, not just individual, level.

Linking sensitive data at the household or family level was seen as a significant opportunity to foster a step change in how we understand and approach both deep-seated and emerging challenges facing the public. The benefits of a family level approach put forward by participants can be divided into two broad categories:

Diagnosis and understanding:

Analysing behaviours, outcomes, opportunities, and inequalities within their social context to develop a complete understanding of factors that drive them and to identify crucial inferences across individuals.

Intervention:

Leveraging this enhanced understanding to develop holistic interventions across family units to tackle some of the most pressing concerns facing the UK public.

38% of use cases combined data across the family group to use the family as the unit of measurement, assessment, and intervention.

For example, participants connected sensitive data to:

Develop family-level interventions to reduce childhood obesity
[\(Use case 6\)](#)

Develop improved domestic abuse interventions
[\(Use case 2\)](#)

Understand the causes of poor mental health among children and young people to develop preventative approaches [\(Use case 4\)](#)

Participants linked data to develop improved interventions for complex problems

By linking sensitive data at scale, participants developed routes to understanding drivers of societal challenges and the reasons for the limited success of existing interventions. Building upon this, they proposed improved solutions and interventions to tackle these problems – not only providing benefits to the public through better outcomes and reduced inequalities, but also to institutions via smarter resource allocation and informed decision making. For example:

Approach	% of use cases	Linking sensitive data allows us to...	Use case example
<p>58%</p>	<p>Create tailored interventions that reflect the unique requirements and circumstances of groups or individuals</p> <p>Allocate resources more efficiently into targeted initiatives that will have maximum impact and engagement</p>	<p>Identifying key bottlenecks within the healthcare system to more effectively allocate resources, reducing time to treatment and diagnosis</p> <p>(Use case 3)</p>	
<p>40%</p>	<p>Better identify risk factors and pinpoint high-risk groups</p> <p>Develop preventative approaches that address root causes and mitigate issues before they arise</p> <p>Shift away from less effective and more expensive reactive approaches</p>	<p>Developing locally optimal low emission zones to prevent future pollution-related ill health</p> <p>(Use case 10)</p>	
<p>23%</p>	<p>Understand the specific factors across individuals and social groups that influence their behaviours</p> <p>Tailor interventions and messaging to different groups to optimally effect behaviour change for public good</p>	<p>Understanding how to reduce vaccine hesitancy and enhance messaging to improve uptake</p> <p>(Use case 9)</p>	

4 / Exemplar opportunities for DARE UK

DARE UK is well-placed to advance research in many, if not all, of the areas surfaced during the workshop.

To maximise the benefit of the programme, and ensure DARE UK's infrastructure supports those use cases that may not otherwise be realised, DARE UK should prioritise those use cases that are:

Tractable

Research objectives that are achievable with enhanced sensitive data connectivity

Cross-domain

Research objectives that link diverse data across jurisdictional and organisational boundaries

High-benefit

Research objectives that have the potential to significantly improve the lives of the UK public

Longitudinal

Research objectives that use retrospective analysis to measure trends and impacts over time

We have curated a selection of 10 use cases to showcase the range of possibilities identified by participants

Through our Use Case Identification Workshop we surfaced 52 distinct use cases for linking sensitive data at scale and across boundaries. Each represents an exciting opportunity to improve lives across society, addressing a broad spectrum of challenges, from improving the air we breath through more effective low emission zones ([Use case 10](#)) to transforming access to primary care for those who need it most ([Use case 7](#)).

While many use cases shared commonalities in data types and desired benefits, each offered unique and innovative approaches to solving complex problems. Following participants' voting and further refinement (see 'Our Approach' section), we have curated a shortlist of 10 use cases that demonstrate the breadth and depth of insights.

These 10 use cases underwent an economic benefit analysis to estimate their potential economic impact if realised.

It is important to note that while this showcase highlights the range of use cases, it does not capture every workshop insight. The data used and desired outcomes are based on inputs provided by participants and may not encompass all possibilities. Further multidisciplinary engagement can uncover new use cases and expand upon those already identified.

The curated use cases link data across all ten data domains and address many of our most pressing challenges

The chart below summarises the data domains linked in each use case and the total number of domains linked:

	Health	Social	Economic	Care and Social System	Climate and Environment	Consumer	Justice	Lifestyle	Commercial	Geographic	Total
Use case 1: Transforming the food economy	█		█		█	█			█		5
Use case 2: Addressing domestic abuse	█	█	█	█			█				5
Use case 3: Reducing NHS bottlenecks	█	█	█								3
Use case 4: Addressing children’s mental health	█	█		█			█				4
Use case 5: Understanding long-term unemployment		█	█	█			█				4
Use case 6: Family interventions to tackle childhood obesity	█	█	█	█		█		█			6
Use case 7: Addressing unmet need and improving access to primary care	█	█	█								3
Use case 8: Balancing healthy diets with sustainable production	█	█			█	█		█	█		6
Use case 9: Improving vaccine uptake	█	█								█	3
Use case 10: Understanding and enhancing low emission zones	█	█			█			█		█	5

Use Case 1: Transforming the food economy

What is the challenge?

Our long-term health and prosperity are deeply linked to our food system – what we eat, what is wasted, what is grown, and how it is grown. Multiple natural and social systems converge to influence our health, sustainability, food security, and natural resilience, yet we lack the clear understanding of these interactions needed to build policy across multiple areas to address these in a more integrated way.

By breaking down sensitive data silos, we can begin to deliver routes to action, mitigating against unintended consequences and delivering far reaching interventions to help us reach net zero, reduce diet-related ill health, and uplift the most deprived groups within society.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

Our society through a food lens:

The complex interactions across the entirety of our food economy and supply chains that have far reaching impacts from Net Zero to food bank use.

Cross cutting routes to action:

How we can develop policies and take action that simultaneously fulfils our diverse food goals to deliver long-term health and prosperity.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	4x	Annual average health and social care costs are approximately four times greater for malnourished individuals (£7408 vs £2155). ⁹
	1.4x	Obese individuals are 1.2-1.6 times more likely to lose working days to sickness. ¹⁰
 Cohorts	17%	Almost 1 in 5 UK households are food insecure, with 2.1 million people living in households that have used food banks in the last 12 months. ¹¹
	£19bn	The UK wastes £19bn worth of food every year, with the average family of four throwing away the equivalent of £1,320 annually. ¹²

How could this benefit the economy?

▶ **£118.4bn** (+/- £28.95bn)

This use case features a broad suite of outcomes encompassing obesity, ill health, sustainability, and malnutrition, which can deliver **over £100bn benefits to 2050**.¹³

What data needs to be linked?

Health

→ Health and health outcomes

Consumer

→ Food bank use
→ Food consumption

Economic

→ Income
→ Deprivation indices
→ Employment
→ Productivity

Commercial

→ Supply chains
→ Agriculture business data

Climate and environment

→ Energy use and production
→ Water use
→ Climate
→ Waste (commercial and household)

Use Case 2: Addressing domestic abuse

What is the challenge?

Despite the significant progress made with the Domestic Abuse Act, instances of domestic abuse remain alarmingly high, with an estimated 2.1 million occurrences annually.¹⁴ Marginalised communities, such as women, children, and LGBTQ+ individuals, are disproportionately affected, and the impacts are profound and long-lasting. Violence experienced or witnessed by children can profoundly affect their educational attainment, prospects, and relationships into adulthood.

Linking diverse, sensitive data will allow us to better understand the impacts of domestic violence on children, as well as the effects of responses such as court proceedings. This can facilitate the development of more comprehensive and effective solutions to prevent violence, support survivors, and challenge societal factors that perpetuate abuse. Ultimately contributing to building a happier, healthier, and more prosperous society for all.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

Whole family journeys through the system:

Quantifying and understanding the impact of domestic abuse and domestic abuse interventions on whole family units.

How to prevent domestic abuse and its effects:

Creating effective mitigation and recovery strategies that reduce domestic abuse incidence and minimise the long-term impact for victims.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	71%	Almost three quarters of the costs of domestic abuse relate to the physical and emotional harm caused. ¹⁵
	14.5%	Domestic abuse is the second most common reason given for losing a home. ¹⁶
 Cohorts	84%	84% of domestic abuse victims in domestic abuse cases are female, with 93% of the defendants male. ¹⁷
	1/5	20% of children in the UK have lived with an adult perpetrating domestic abuse. ¹⁸

How could this benefit the economy?

▶ **£17.66bn** (+/- £5.89bn)

A 1-2% reduction in incidents of domestic abuse could provide **~£18bn economic benefits to 2050.**¹⁹

What data needs to be linked?

Health

- GP records
- Health and health outcomes
- Hospital episodes

Care and social system

- Social care and service interactions
- Local authority

Justice

- Family justice
- Courts and criminal justice

Economic

- Deprivation indices

Social

- Education
- Family composition

Use Case 3:

Reducing NHS bottlenecks

What is the challenge?

With 6.37 million people currently on NHS waiting lists, many endure avoidable pain and disruption to their daily lives while anxiously awaiting diagnosis and treatment.²⁰ Exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, these lists have been steadily growing since 2013, straining resources and causing targets to be missed.²¹

As individuals suffer while waiting for treatment and diagnosis, communities and the economy both feel the impact. Individuals' quality of life is diminished, their capacity to participate in society limited, and ability to stay in work reduced. Connecting sensitive data can help policy makers identify and tackle bottlenecks in the health and care system – enhancing capacity, improving resource allocation, and expediting access to essential care.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

The location and cause of bottlenecks:

Taking a system-wide view to identify key capacity constraints and their dependencies, linking individual health, hospital operations, and social data to pinpoint underlying drivers.

How can we reduce these bottlenecks:

Developing solutions that improve resource allocation and optimise interventions to increase capacity and reduce waiting lists.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	3.3m	3.3 million individuals are waiting longer than the target 18 weeks from referral to treatment. ²²
	1%	For every 1% increase in capacity, 565 million patient years are saved, which would otherwise have been spent waiting. ²³
 Cohorts	£5bn	With time freed up to work, look after children, and care for relatives, each % increase in capacity represents almost £5bn in increased productivity. ²⁴
	2.1x	People in the most deprived areas are more than twice as likely to wait over a year for elective care. ²⁵

How could this benefit the economy?

▶ **£20.92bn** (+/- £6.97bn)

A 5-10% increase in capacity via bottleneck reduction can result in ~£21bn benefit to the UK economy over the next 5 years.^{26 27}

What data needs to be linked?

Health

- Health and health outcomes
- GP records
- Hospital episodes
- Hospital occupancy
- Referral times
- Waiting times
- Healthcare utilisation
- Access to GP appointments

Economic

- Benefits
- Employment

Social

- Demographic
- Disability

Use Case 4: Addressing children's mental health

What is the challenge?

As our awareness of mental health issues grows, so too does the recognition of the unique struggles children encounter. In the last three years alone, the likelihood of young people having mental health problems has increased by 50%, with profound consequences for their relationships, physical well-being, and job prospects across their entire lives.²⁸

Against the backdrop of already stretched resources – ~75% of young people with mental health challenges are not getting the help they need – sensitive data connectivity can provide a solution.²⁹ By identifying key risk factors to develop preventative and integrated solutions, we can address issues before they escalate. Analysis of linked sensitive mental health data has the power to help deliver cost effective, targeted children's mental health support, alleviating hardship for individuals and communities alike, both in childhood and throughout adulthood.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

Early indicators and risk patterns:

Identifying the key combinations of factors that result in poor children's mental health before they present themselves.

How to prevent long-term crises:

Developing preventative strategies to mitigate children's mental health issues and intervene in challenges early before they have life-long impacts.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	5	5 children (1/6) in every classroom in the UK were identified as having a probable mental health problem. ³⁰
	50%	Approximately half of all adult mental health conditions are established by age 14. ³¹
 Cohorts	4.5x	Children in the lowest income quintile are 4.5 times more likely to experience severe mental health problems than those in the highest. ³²
	27%	The number of young people suffering from anxiety doubled during the COVID-19 pandemic from 13% to 27%. ³³

How could this benefit the economy?

▶ **£21.92bn** (+/- £7.31bn)

A 5-10% reduction in children's mental health challenges (age 0-14) can result in almost £22bn of economic benefits to 2050.³⁴

What data needs to be linked?

Health

- GP records
- Mental health
- Wearables

Care and social system

- Social care and service interactions

Justice

- Police
- Home office
- Courts and criminal justice

Social

- Well-being
- Education
- Mood monitoring apps

Use Case 5: Understanding long-term unemployment

What is the challenge?

Long-term unemployment, defined as those out of and actively seeking work for over a year, presents significant material and psychological challenges for the 262,000 individuals in this position.³⁵ Faced with financial strain, social isolation, and skills atrophy, a vicious cycle is created. Resulting in an inability to participate productively in the economy, exacerbating inequalities, and leading to significant hardship.

Sensitive data, linked at scale, presents an opportunity to understand the social, economic, and structural issues that are driving long-term unemployment. Enabling comprehensive, integrated solutions that address the problem at source, delivering substantial benefits to both individuals and society. By tackling root causes, we can also impact the nearly 1.9 million economically inactive individuals who would like to be employed.³⁶

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

What is causing long-term unemployment:

Evaluating the complex, often lifelong causes of long-term unemployment and understanding the factors that prevent individuals from entering or re-joining the workforce quickly.

How to get people into work:

Developing effective strategies to address root causes of long-term unemployment and prevent individuals from falling out of employment.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	5x	Unemployed people are 5 times as likely to report poor health compared to employed individuals. ³⁷
	1/5	20% of economically inactive individuals wish to return to work but are unable to do so due to factors including long term sickness and caring for relatives. ³⁸
 Cohorts	24%	Of long-term unemployed individuals are aged 24 and under, representing a substantial difficulty for many to gain entry to the job market. ³⁹
	2x	Adults from Pakistani, Bangladeshi, Black/Black British and mixed ethnicity backgrounds are more than twice as likely to be unemployed as white adults. ⁴⁰

How could this benefit the economy?

▶ **£28.68bn** (+/- £9.56bn)

A 5-10% reduction in long-term unemployment and a 1-2% reduction in economic inactivity can deliver ~£29bn in economic benefits to 2050.⁴¹

What data needs to be linked?

Economic

- Employment
- Income
- Tax
- Deprivation indices
- Job satisfaction
- Sick leave
- Productivity

Care and social system

- Social care interactions

Social

- Education
- Housing
- Geographic opportunities

Use Case 6: Family interventions to tackle childhood obesity

What is the challenge?

Where and how children grow up, as well as who they grow up with, profoundly influences their health. Focusing on families, whether biological or social, opens new avenues for addressing stubborn challenges, especially childhood obesity. Early interventions within the family unit can prevent lifelong health issues, enhance quality of life, and raise productivity across society.

Childhood obesity considerably raises the risk of obesity in adulthood, and related health issue such as chronic illnesses, reduced healthy lifespans, and premature mortality. With 22.7% of Year 6 pupils currently obese, using sensitive data to design holistic family-centred interventions can significantly lessen the healthcare and financial burdens on individuals and society.⁴²

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

Why obesity happens:

How complex interactions of health, economic, and social drivers across each member of the family unit influence the health of a child from birth.

What works for families:

Developing integrated and holistic approaches that reflect the diversity of family situations to create environments that support children's health.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	£62,000	An obese individual will incur ~£62,000 in quality of life losses throughout their lifetime due to obesity. ⁴³
	~72.5%	60-85% of obese children remain obese into adulthood, increasing their risk of future ill health and reduced quality of life. ⁴⁴
 Cohorts	2x	Children in deprived areas are twice as likely to be obese than those in more affluent areas. ⁴⁵
	3%	Obesity costs UK society £74bn annually, equal to 3% of GDP. ⁴⁶

How could this benefit the economy?

▶ **£8.9bn** (+/- £2.31bn)

A 10-15% reduction in childhood obesity can generate a combined ~£9bn in healthcare savings, productivity and quality of life increases to 2050.⁴⁷

What data needs to be linked?

Health

- Health and health outcomes
- Genetic

Consumer

- Shopping habits
- Food consumption

Economic

- Employment
- Benefits
- Deprivation indices

Care and social system

- Social care interactions
- Administrative data

Social

- Demographic
- Education
- Family composition

Lifestyle

- Diet
- Physical activity

Use Case 7: Addressing unmet need and improving access to primary care

What is the challenge?

Identifying and addressing unmet need within the NHS is vital for improving healthcare outcomes and optimising resource allocation. By pinpointing where gaps exist, identifying underserved populations, and understanding why individuals aren't accessing services when they need to, we can tailor interventions to effectively bridge disparities and provide routes to primary care.

With an estimated 7 million people on the 'hidden' NHS waiting list – needing care but not on official lists – there is a significant opportunity to improve quality of life and health outcomes, delivering broad societal and economic benefits.⁴⁸ Linking sensitive data can help uncover these unmet needs and enable a more efficient allocation of resources to deliver the right care, where and when it is needed most. Alleviating sickness, reducing inequalities, and enhancing productive potential.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

Where need exists:

Identifying individuals and cohorts who need support from NHS services but are not receiving it, not receiving it fast enough, or not aware they need it.

How to address this need:

Developing optimised solutions that deliver access to healthcare when and where it is needed, in a way that responds to individuals' social and economic situations.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	58%	58% of people who refrained from making a GP appointment (reasons include employment and not wanting to burden the NHS) reported a negative impact on their health. ⁴⁹
	50.2%	Over half of patients find it 'not easy at all' or 'not very easy' to get through to someone at their GP practice. ⁵⁰
 Cohorts	14.4%	There are almost 15% more patients per GP in deprived areas. But with 7.8 GPs per 10,000 compared the OECD average of 10.8, limited access has an impact across society. ⁵¹
	£150bn	Ill health in working age people costs the economy an estimated £150bn annually in lost productivity. ⁵²

How could this benefit the economy?

► **£20.63bn** (+/- £6.88bn)

A 0.5-1% reduction in waiting lists and ill health via improved diagnosis and access, can deliver ~£21bn in economic benefits to 2050.⁵³

What data needs to be linked?

Health

- Health and health outcomes
- Healthcare utilisation
- Access to GP appointments
- Mental health

Economic

- Employment

Social

- Demographic
- Education

Use Case 8: Balancing healthy diets with sustainable production

What is the challenge?

Achieving a balance between healthy diets and sustainable food production is crucial for both human health and the environment. Healthy diets play a key role in preventing chronic diseases and reducing obesity, which costs society £74 billion annually.⁵⁴ However, our current food production methods often harm the environment through excessive resource use, greenhouse gas emissions, and loss of biodiversity.

Understanding how healthy diets and sustainable food production intersect will help us develop comprehensive solutions that prioritise long-term human and environmental well-being. By harnessing the power of linked sensitive data, we can find the optimal middle-ground and implement effective behavioural change interventions. Empowered by data, we can learn to live in a way that benefits both ourselves and the world around us.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

What optimal diets look like:

Tackling the trade-off between health and sustainability to understand what diets and food types can maximise both objectives.

How to influence behaviour change:

Developing strategies that reflect population diversity to effectively encourage a popular shift to more optimal diets.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	3/5	62% of Britons have already altered their diets to get healthier, however two thirds of the adult population is currently overweight. ⁵⁵
	13%	Unhealthy diets account for 13% of all deaths in the UK. ⁵⁶
 Cohorts	43%	The poorest fifth of UK households would need to spend 43% of their disposable income on food to meet the cost of the government recommended healthy diet. ⁵⁷
	£13bn	Poor diet related ill health costs the NHS an estimated £12.8bn annually. ⁵⁸

How could this benefit the economy?

► **£34.31bn** (+/- £11.4bn)

Moving towards sustainable, healthy diets can provide an economic benefit of ~34bn to 2050, through reduced obesity, ill health, and costs of climate change.⁵⁹

What data needs to be linked?

Health

→ Health and health outcomes

Lifestyle

→ Diet

Consumer

→ Food consumption

Climate and environment

→ Pollution
→ Climate
→ Energy use and production

Social

→ Education

Commercial

→ Supply chains

Use Case 9: Improving vaccine uptake

What is the challenge?

Despite the successful rollout of the COVID-19 vaccine, with 88% of the population aged 12 and over receiving at least two doses, the pandemic has revealed a concerning trend of increasing vaccine hesitancy and disparities in vaccine acceptance across society.⁶⁰ Vaccination rates for preventable diseases in the UK have been declining, with the MMR uptake at 85%, the lowest since 2010-11, contributing to recent outbreaks.⁶¹

The rise in vaccine scepticism, fuelled by the COVID-19 pandemic and influences such as social media, has led the UK to fall short of the 95% uptake levels needed for herd immunity.⁶² By linking sensitive data across health and social sectors, we can better understand the factors driving vaccine hesitancy to help inform government messaging and intervention policies.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

What limits vaccine uptake:

The myriad forces that influence individuals' and cohorts' vaccine hesitancy, both for scheduled vaccines and during unplanned pandemics.

How to refine messaging to improve uptake:

Tailoring messaging to diverse population cohorts to encourage vaccine uptake, maintaining the UK's herd immunity and enhancing pandemic preparedness.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	1/5	Although only 3% of the population is 'anti-vax', it is estimated that 20% of the population exhibit some signs of vaccine hesitancy towards COVID-19 vaccines. ⁶³
	£160	Every single incidence of MMR vaccine refusal could cost society £162.21. ⁶⁴
 Cohorts	10%	Vaccine rates are almost 10% lower than WHO targets, preventing us from eradicating preventable diseases such as measles. ⁶⁵
	£34	For every £1 spent on health protection measures that include immunisation the return on investment is estimated to be £34. ⁶⁶

How could this benefit the economy?

► **£1.4bn** (+/- £0.47bn)

Improving scheduled vaccine uptake by 5-10% can drive benefits of £1.4bn to the UK economy by 2050. With additional benefits of ~£200m in the event of a pandemic event.⁶⁷

What data needs to be linked?

Social

- Education
- Demographic
- Trust in govt.
- Social media use
- Interactions with government communications

Health

- Health and health outcomes

Geographic

- Vaccination centre locations and accessibility

Use Case 10: Understanding and enhancing low emission zones

What is the challenge?

Researchers estimate that over 48,000 adults die prematurely each year in the UK due to particulate matter pollution.⁶⁸

A key underlying factor of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, air pollution presents a substantial public health concern, with low emission zones (LEZs) seen as a vital route to reducing emissions and improving quality of life.

A relatively recent introduction, understanding the impact of low emission zones is essential for enhancing their effectiveness in improving air quality. Linking sensitive data across health, social, environmental, and economic jurisdictions will enable policy makers to develop local strategies that respond to the needs of communities whilst cutting emissions. Not only enhancing quality of life across society and improving planetary health, but also driving productivity gains through reduced illness-related absences.

Linking sensitive data can help us understand:

The impact of low emission zones:

Understanding the long and short term impact that LEZs have on a range of factors including health, productivity, education outcomes, and transport use.

How to maximise effectiveness:

Developing optimal local solutions that reduce particulate pollution whilst responding to the needs of local populations.

Why is it important?

 Individuals	14.3%	Evidence shows that low emission zones reduce the likelihood of sick days by 14.3%. ⁶⁹
	1/20	5.3% of UK deaths can be attributed to long-term exposure to small particles polluting the air. ⁷⁰
 Cohorts	3x	Air pollution has approximately twice the impact on lung function decline and three times the increased COPD risk on lower income individuals. ⁷¹
	£25bn	Cardiovascular disease has an economic burden of £25bn annually, with evidence from existing LEZs suggesting this can be reduced by 2-3%. ⁷²

How could this benefit the economy?

► **£38.57bn** (+/- £3.67bn)

The implementation of a locally effective LEZs covering the entire urban population can deliver economic benefits of ~£39bn by 2050.⁷³

What data needs to be linked?

Health

→ Health and health outcomes

Lifestyle

→ Transport (including modes, ownership, and mobility)

Geographic

→ Location
→ Urban planning

Climate and environment

→ Air pollution
→ Weather

Social

→ Demographic
→ Education

5 / Conclusions and next steps

Conclusions

The use cases surfaced here evidenced high demand for access to a plethora of 80 different kinds of sensitive and non-sensitive data, including widespread demand for health data (especially data on mental health), economic and social data (particularly data on employment, income, deprivation and benefits), as well as more emerging types of behavioural data on things like diet and consumer spending.

A number of UKRI research infrastructure programmes across the UK research landscape are working to provide researchers access to de-identified versions of these datasets, including Health Data Research UK (focusing on health data), Administrative Data Research UK (focusing on the provision of government administrative data for research, as well as data linkage programmes to generate re-useable 'research-ready' linked datasets), Smart Data Research UK (a new ESRC research infrastructure programme looking to provide access to 'smart data' from things like wearable devices), and the UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration (longitudinal survey data and linkages, widely considered an area of particular strength for the UK), to name a few.

“ I particularly enjoyed interacting with the other participants - from a wide variety of disciplines and experience levels and each made significant contributions to the small groups. ”

Workshop participant

Each of these programmes is strengthened by their domain-expertise and focus on handling and providing access to particular types of data. However, over 65% of the use-cases highlighted in this report needed data from three

or more domains, which would require connecting data from across different research programme domains – precisely the capabilities that the DARE UK programme is looking to support. As described in the DARE UK Phase 1 Recommendations report, building a coordinated national research infrastructure for sensitive data to enable this sort of cross-cutting research will require overcoming considerable technical, governance and skills challenges alongside bringing together the people with the diversity of expertise needed to properly analyse and interpret results from the data. The DARE UK programme and the wider research infrastructure community need to embrace the cultural shift to interdisciplinary working through supporting a growing community of diverse researchers and members of the public

united in an interest in the use of sensitive data to address cross-cutting societal challenges. Mechanisms to grow and sustain this community could be through direct funding through infrastructure research grants such as previous DARE UK projects (see sprint exemplar and driver project portfolios) or community group funding, but also through the provision of collaboration opportunities (building on this workshop, for example) to bring researchers together with the public to co-create research proposals and take them forward for funding. It is essential that these activities continue to involve the public throughout to help ensure that public benefit, as understood and defined by the public, remains the driving force behind progress towards a trustworthy national coordinated research infrastructure.

“I’d like to see a move towards Sandpits where linkage studies are funded after all the talking.”

Workshop participant

Even in the short period of time of six hours of collaborative discourse and activities between 50+ individuals, we were able to surface over 50 different use-cases, tackling some of the most persistent and pressing societal challenges as wide-ranging as food system sustainability and security, the mental health crisis (particularly in children and young people), and poor population vaccination uptake. This is clearly only scratching the surface of potential use cases that data connectivity can enable - expanding these discussions to incorporate additional research disciplines, alongside representatives from government, industry and the public, would help further uncover the broad range of potential DARE UK and the sensitive data research infrastructure community can unlock. Together, the breadth and depth of the research opportunity as well as potential economic benefits (modelled at roughly £319.11bn (+/-79.14) to 2050 for just a subset of 10 use-cases) exemplified in these use-cases should galvanize support from funders, data owners, and infrastructure and services providers to work together with the DARE UK programme to support capabilities to connect different types of sensitive data at scale and put the UK at the forefront of cross-cutting sensitive data research.

“I would quite like to see something more tangible. I think if we were to convince the public that this was time and money well spent, then the public would want to see some tangible outcomes. They would want to know the answer to the ‘so what?’ question. What happens next? What do we do with all this information? Where do we go from here?”

Workshop participant

Next steps

As the DARE UK programme moves into the next phase, it is critical, as evidenced by this work, that the programme support the delivery of real-world interdisciplinary data research studies that span traditional research boundaries and positively impact our collective understanding of intersectional societal challenges.

This work has shaped the proposal for the next phase of DARE UK, providing part of the strategic context for the DARE UK programme. It will feed directly into three important areas of work in the next phase of the programme.

1

This work will be used to **inform and define** the specifications of funding opportunities for research teams whose ambitions are to begin tackling the sorts of scientific use-cases laid out in this report – details will be forthcoming, please sign up to the DARE UK mailing list to stay informed.

2

This work has already **catalysed conversations** at a senior leadership level across various data research initiatives and funders around improving the coherence and coordination across UKRI sensitive data research investments. DARE UK will continue to play its part in driving this strategic alignment together with its partners and with support from outputs of activities such as this.

3

This work has **emphasised the importance** and value of building communities around shared interests, in this case researchers tackling ambitious intersectional societal challenges through the linkage of sensitive and non-sensitive data for research. The programme has already provided funding for such community building activities, continuing to support communities to network, foster the sharing of information and best practices, and co-define research priorities that align with the DARE UK programme's vision is important. In the next phase the programme will continue to provide small, focused funding opportunities to support this.

Part of the purpose of the DARE UK programme is fundamentally to drive and support the cultural change of the UK sensitive data ecosystem as it transitions towards a more federated, distributed, interdisciplinary landscape.

Research use-cases such as those outlined in this report and the underpinning technological innovations supporting them can propel this cultural shift forward and catalyse the convergence of interdisciplinary communities, breaking down traditional research silos while delivering research impact and public benefit.

6 / Appendices

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Appendix 2: Use case long-list

	Health	Social	Economic	Lifestyle	Consumer	Geographic	Climate and environment	Care and social system	Justice	Commercial	Total
Use case 1: Transforming the food economy											5
Use case 2: Addressing domestic abuse											5
Use case 3: Reducing NHS bottlenecks											3
Use case 4: Addressing children’s mental health											4
Use case 5: Understanding long-term unemployment											4
Use case 6: Family interventions to tackle childhood obesity											6
Use case 7: Addressing unmet need and improving access to primary care											3
Use case 8: Balancing healthy diets with sustainable production											6
Use case 9: Improving vaccine uptake											3
Use case 10: Understanding and enhancing low emission zones											5

	Health	Social	Economic	Lifestyle	Consumer	Geographic	Climate and environment	Care and social system	Justice	Commercial	Total
Use case 11: Understanding how to encourage economic growth											5
Use case 12: Understanding the effect of housing on health outcomes											2
Use case 13: Linking education, employment, and mental health data to improve mental health and educational attainment											3
Use case 14: Changing behaviours and challenging assumptions around energy use											3
Use case 15: Better understanding the factors affecting productivity											2
Use case 16: Understanding the triggers for poor mental health and identifying at risk groups											6
Use case 17: Improving contraception to meet women's needs											1
Use case 18: Understanding the root causes of long-term ill health and developing more holistic solutions											4
Use case 19: Getting the correct care where it is needed and enabling better self-management of conditions											2
Use case 20: Understanding the causes of demand to improve access and uptake for mental health services											4

	Health	Social	Economic	Lifestyle	Consumer	Geographic	Climate and environment	Care and social system	Justice	Commercial	Total
Use case 21: Understanding the effect of inequality in respite care on mental health											2
Use case 22: Improving speed and access to health services, and enhancing integrated care											4
Use case 23: Understanding the impact of different modes of transport on health											3
Use case 24: Understanding online relationships and their influences on individuals and society											2
Use case 25: Identifying areas of discrimination and assessing how discrimination impacts quality of life											2
Use case 26: Understanding the reality vs what is reported to optimise health interventions											1
Use case 27: Helping graduates explore new jobs and improve search elements based upon skills and experience											2
Use case 28: Achieving economies of scope and scale for local councils											2
Use case 29: Improving monitoring and intervention of health conditions at home for the elderly											2

	Health	Social	Economic	Lifestyle	Consumer	Geographic	Climate and environment	Care and social system	Justice	Commercial	Total
Use case 30: Providing comprehensive, tailored support for social and MH challenges via a single point of support											3
Use case 31: Understanding relationship between food, education, and health outcomes											4
Use case 32: Understanding the impact that energy and climate has on personal finances and health outcomes											3
Use case 33: Understanding the causes of obesity to help make more targeted interventions											5
Use case 34: Understanding of the short- and long-term impacts of vaping											3
Use case 35: Understand how children’s environments affect health and education outcomes											4
Use case 36: Understand impact of screen time on children’s short- and long-term outcomes, particularly mental health and social effects											5
Use case 37: Understanding affordability of Net Zero 2050 requirements and developing the optimal incentives to achieve this											5
Use case 38: Understanding businesses resilience to climate change, boosting productivity, and predicting the success/failures of businesses											2

	Health	Social	Economic	Lifestyle	Consumer	Geographic	Climate and environment	Care and social system	Justice	Commercial	Total
Use case 39: Understanding impact of income volatility on mental health											2
Use case 40: Understand the impact of low and ultra-low emission zones on different groups											6
Use case 41: Developing early interventions for mental health challenges											3
Use case 42: Training AI models to detect colon cancer more effectively using colonoscopy data											2
Use case 43: Understanding the interaction of work status on mental health and vice versa											2
Use case 44: Understanding the impacts of ASD and ADHD diagnoses on education outcomes and enhancing screening and support											2
Use case 45: Understanding the factors that contribute to inequalities in lung cancer care and impact access to care											4
Use case 46: Predicting disease before any symptoms present and developing new treatments based on new biomarkers											5
Use case 47: Understand the consequences of court decisions											3
Use case 48: Identifying high risk groups for respiratory disease											5

	Health	Social	Economic	Lifestyle	Consumer	Geographic	Climate and environment	Care and social system	Justice	Commercial	Total
Use case 49: Understanding how shopping habits affects health											4
Use case 50: Understanding how the ability to travel to green space impacts upon mental health											4
Use case 51: Understanding access to higher education for different groups and the factors that can enable or limit access											4
Use case 52: Understanding the factors that most influence cardo-vascular disease and developing targeted interventions for high-risk groups											5

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The methodology for The PSC's analysis is described on page 12, 'Desk Research', in this report. All analyses are based on the references listed for each use case.

Appendix 4: Economic Benefit Model References

Use Case 1: Transforming the food economy

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Use Case 3: Reducing NHS Bottlenecks

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Use Case 6: Family interventions to tackle childhood obesity

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Use Case 8: Balancing health diets with sustainable production

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